

SMARANDACHE – R-MODULE AND COMMUTATIVE AND BOUNDED BE-ALGEBRAS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we introduced Smarandache – 2 – algebraic structure of R-Module namely Smarandache – R-Module. A Smarandache – 2 – algebraic structure on a set N means a weak algebraic structure A_0 on N such that there exist a proper subset M of N , which is embedded with a stronger algebraic structure A_1 , stronger algebraic structure means satisfying more axioms, by proper subset one understands a subset different from the empty set, from the unit element if any, from the whole set. We define Smarandache – R-Module and obtain some of its characterization through Commutative and Bounded BE-Algebras. For basic concepts we refers to Florentin smarandache[2] and Raul Padilla[9].

Keyword: R-Module, Smarandache – R-Module, BE-Algebras.

1.INTRODUCTION

New notions are introduced in algebra to study more about the congruence in number theory by Florentin smarandache[2]. By <proper subset> of a set A , We consider a set P included in A and different from A , different from the empty set, and from the unit element in A – if any they rank the algebraic structures using an order relationship.

The algebraic structures $S_1 \ll S_2$ if :both are defined on the same set \therefore all S_1 laws are also S_2 laws; all axioms of S_1 law are accomplished by the corresponding S_2 law; S_2 law strictly accomplishes more axioms than S_1 laws, or in other words S_2 laws has more laws than S_1 .

For example : semi group \ll monoid \ll group \ll ring \ll field, or Semi group \ll commutative semi group, ring \ll unitary ring, etc. they define a General special structure to be a structure SM on a set A , different from a structure SN , such that a proper subset of A is an SN structure, where $SM \ll SN$.

2. Prerequisites

Definition 2.1: An algebra $(A; *, 1)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a BE-algebra if for all x, y and z in A ,

$$(BE1) \quad x * x = 1$$

$$(BE2) \quad x * 1 = 1$$

$$(BE3) \quad 1 * x = x$$

$$(BE4) \quad x * (y * z) = y * (x * z).$$

In A , a binary relation “ \leq ” is defined by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 1$.

Definition 2.2: A BE-algebra $(X; *, 1)$ is said to be self-distributive if $x * (y * z) = (x * y) * (x * z)$ for all x, y and $z \in A$.

Definition 2.3: A dual BCK-algebra is an algebra $(A; *, 1)$ of type $(2,0)$ satisfying (BE1) and (BE2) and the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in A$.

$$(dBCK1) \quad x * y = y * x = 1 \text{ implies } x = y$$

$$(dBCK2) \quad (x * y) * ((y * z) * (x * z)) = 1$$

$$(dBCK3) \quad x * ((x * y) * y) = 1.$$

Definition 2.4: Let A be a BE-algebra or dual BCK-algebra. A is said to be commutative if the following identity holds:

$$x \vee_B y = y \vee_B x \text{ where } x \vee_B y = (y * x) * x \text{ for all } x, y \in A.$$

Definition 2.5: Let A be a BE-algebra. If there exists an element 0 satisfying $0 \leq x$ (or $0 * x = 1$) for all $x \in A$, then the element “ 0 ” is called unit of A . A BE-algebra with unit is called a bounded BE-algebra.

Note : In a bounded BE-algebra $x * 0$ denoted by xN .

Definition 2.6: In a bounded BE-algebra, the element x such that $xNN = x$ is called an involution .

Let $S(A) = \{x \in A ; xNN = x\}$ where A is a bounded BE-algebra. $S(A)$ is the set of all involutions in A . Moreover, since $1NN = (1 * 0) * 0 = 0 * 0 = 1$ and $0NN = (0 * 0) * 0 = 1 * 0 = 0$, We have $0, 1 \in S(A)$ and so $S(A) \neq \emptyset$.

Definition 2.7: Each of the elements a and b in a bounded BE-algebra is called the complement of the other if $a \vee b = 1$ and $a \wedge b = 0$.

Definition 2.8: Now we have introduced our concept smarandache – R – module : “ Let R be a module, called R -module. If R is said to be smarandache – R – module. Then there exist a proper subset A of R which is an algebra with respect to the same induced operations of R .”

3.Theorem

Theorem 3.1: Let R be a smarandache-R-module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, then the following conditions are satisfied,

- (i) $1N = 0, 0N = 1$
- (ii) $x \leq xNN$
- (iii) $x * yN = y * xN$
- (iv) $0 \vee x = xNN, x \vee 0 = x$.

Proof. Let R be a smarandache-R-module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is bounded BE-algebras.

(i) We have $1N = 1*0 = 0$ and $0N = 0 * 0 = 1$. by using (BE1) and (BE3)

(ii) Since $x * xNN = x * ((x * 0) * 0) = (x * 0) * (x * 0) = 1$

We get $x \leq x$ (by (BE1) and (BE4))

(iii) We have $x * yN = x * (y * 0)$ (by using (BE4))

$$= y * (x * 0)$$

$$= y * xN.$$

(iv) By routine operations, we have $0 \vee x = (x * 0) * 0 = xNN$ and $x \vee 0 = (0 * x) * x = 1 * x = x$.

Theorem 3.2: Let R be a smarandache-R-module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, then the following conditions are satisfied $x * y \leq (y \vee x) * y$ for all $x, y \in A$.

Proof. Let R be a smarandache-R-module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is bounded BE-algebras.

Since

$$(x * y) * ((y \vee x) * y) = (y \vee x) * ((x * y) * y) = (y \vee x) * (y \vee x) = 1$$

We have $x * y \leq (y \vee x) * y$.

Theorem 3.3: Let R be a smarandache-R-module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, In addition to that satisfy $x * (y * z) = (x * y) * (x * z)$ then the following conditions are

satisfied for all $x, y, z \in A$

$$(i) x * y \leq yN * xN$$

$$(ii) x \leq y \text{ implies } yN \leq xN.$$

Proof. Since R be a smarandache-R-module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is bounded and Self-Distributive BE-algebras.

(i) Since $(x * y) * (yN * xN)$

$$= (x * y) * ((y * 0) * (x * 0))$$

$$= (y * 0) * ((x * y) * (x * 0)) \text{ (by BE4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= (y * 0) * (x * (y * 0)) \text{ (by distributivity)} \\
&= x * ((y * 0) * (y * 0)) \text{ (by BE4)} \\
&= x * 1 \text{ (by BE1)} \\
&= 1 \text{ (by BE2) ,}
\end{aligned}$$

We have $x * y \leq yN * xN$.

- (ii) It is trivial by $x \leq y$, We have $z * x \leq z * y$
then $y * z \leq x * z$ for all $x, y, z \in A$.

Theorem 3.4: Let R be a smarandache-R-module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, In addition to that satisfy $x * (y * z) = (x * y) * (x * z)$, then the following conditions are satisfied

- (i) $(y \vee x) * y \leq x * y$.
(ii) $x * (x * y) = x * y$.

Proof. Since R be a smarandache-R-module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is a Self-Distributive BE-algebras.

(i) Since

$$\begin{aligned}
x * (y \vee x) &= x * ((x * y) * y) \\
&= (x * y) * (x * y) \\
&= 1.
\end{aligned}$$

We have $x \leq y \vee x$. By $z * x \leq z * y$

We have $(y \vee x) * y \leq x * y$ for all $x, y, z \in A$

(ii) By using self distributive definition, (BE1) and (BE3), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
x * (x * y) &= (x * x) * (x * y) \\
&= 1 * (x * y) \\
&= x * y.
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.5: Let R be a smarandache-R-module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, In addition to that satisfy $0 \leq x$ (or $0 * x = 1$), then the following conditions are satisfied for all $x, y \in A$

- (i) $xNN = x$
(ii) $xN \wedge yN = (x \vee y)$

- (iii) $xN \vee yN = (x \wedge y)$
- (iv) $xN * yN = y * x$.

Proof. Since R be a smarandache-R-module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is a bounded and Commutative BE-algebras.

(i) It is obtained that

$$\begin{aligned} xNN &= (x * 0) * 0 \text{ (from BE3)} \\ &= (0 * x) * x \text{ (by commutativity)} \\ &= 1 * x \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) By the definition of “ \wedge ” and (i) we have that

$$xN \wedge yN = (xNN \vee yNN)N = (x \vee y)N.$$

(iii) By the definition of “ \wedge ” and (i) we have that

$$(x \wedge y)N = (xN \vee yN)NN = xN \vee yN.$$

(iv) We have $xN * yN = (x * 0) * (y * 0)$

$$\begin{aligned} &= y * ((x * 0) * 0) \\ &= y * (xNN) = y * x. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.6: Let R be a smarandache-R-module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, In addition to that, there exists a complement of any element of A and then it is unique.

Proof. Since R be a smarandache-R-module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is a bounded and Commutative BE-algebras.

Let $x \in A$ and a, b be two complements of x . Then we know that $x \wedge a = x \wedge b = 0$ and $x \vee a = x \vee b = 1$.

Also since $x \vee a = (x * a) * a = 1$ and $a * (x * a) = x * (a * a) = x * 1 = 1$,

We have $x * a \leq a$ and $a \leq x * a$. So we get $x * a = a$.

Similarly

$$x * b = b.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence } a * b &= (x * a) * (x * b) = (aN * xN) * (bN * xN) \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (iv)} \\ &= bN * ((aN * xN) * xN) \text{ by BE-4} \\ &= bN * (xN \vee aN) \\ &= bN * (x \wedge a) N \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (iii)} \\ &= (x \wedge a) * b \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (iii)} \\ &= 0 * b \\ &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

With similar operations, we have $b * a = 1$.

Hence we obtain $a = b$ which gives that the complement of x is unique.

Theorem 3.7: Let R be a smarandache- R -module, if there exists a proper subset A of R in which (BE1) to (BE4) are hold, In addition to that satisfy $0 \leq x$ (or $0 * x = 1$), then the following conditions are equivalent for all $x, y \in A$

- (i) $x \wedge xN = 0$
- (ii) $xN \vee x = 1$
- (iii) $xN * x = x$
- (iv) $x * xN = xN$
- (v) $x * (x * y) = x * y$.

Proof. Since R be a smarandache- R -module. Then by definition there exists a proper subset A of R which is an algebra. By hypothesis A holds for (BE1) to (BE4) then A is a Commutative and bounded BE-algebras.

- (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $x \wedge xN = 0$. Then it follows that
- $$\begin{aligned} xN \vee x &= (xN \vee x) \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (i)} \\ &= (xNN \wedge xN) \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (ii)} \\ &= (x \wedge xN) \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (i)} \\ &= 0N \\ &= 1. \end{aligned}$$
- (ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Let $xN \vee x = 1$. Then, since
- $$\begin{aligned} (xN * x) * x &= x \vee xN = 1 \text{ and} \\ x * (xN * x) &= xN * (x * x) = xN * 1 = 1 \end{aligned}$$
- We get $xN * x = x$ by (dBCK1).
- (iii) \Rightarrow (iv) Let $xN * x = x$. Substituting xN for x and using Theorem 2.5 (i) We obtain the result.
- (iv) \Rightarrow (v) Let $x * xN = xN$. Then
- $$\begin{aligned} \text{We get } yN * (x * xN) &= yN * xN. \\ \text{Hence we have } x * (yN * xN) &= yN * xN. \text{ Using Theorem 2.5 (iv)} \\ \text{We obtain } x * (x * y) &= x * y. \end{aligned}$$
- (v) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $x * (x * y) = x * y$. Then
- $$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } xN \vee x &= (x * (xN)) * xN \\ &= (x * (x * 0)) * xN \\ &= (x * 0) * (x * 0) \\ &= 1. \end{aligned}$$
- (ii) \Rightarrow (i) Let $xN \vee x = 1$. Then
- $$\begin{aligned} \text{We obtain } N \wedge x &= xN \wedge xNN \\ &= (x \vee xN) \text{ by Theorem 2.5 (ii)} \\ &= 1N \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

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